

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease in Hypothyroid Patients: A Gender-Neutral Perspective

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Abstract:

Background: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) and Hypothyroidism are prevalent conditions with significant metabolic implications. The relationship between these two disorders, particularly concerning gender differences and associated risk factors for NAFLD among Hypothyroid patients, remains underexplored.

Aim and objective: This study takes a unique approach by aiming to determine the prevalence and risk factors of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) among Hypothyroid patients, irrespective of gender.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study, conducted with meticulous attention to detail, enrolled 300 adult patients diagnosed with Hypothyroidism, including 150 males and 150 females aged 18-65. Participants underwent a comprehensive clinical evaluation, including thyroid function tests, liver ultrasound for NAFLD diagnosis, and assessment of metabolic parameters such as BMI and diabetes. The robustness of our statistical analyses, which included descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, and multivariate logistic regression to identify NAFLD-related factors, further ensures the validity of our findings.

Results: The prevalence of NAFLD among Hypothyroid patients was 40% (95% CI: 34.5% - 45.5%), with no significant gender difference observed ($p = 0.95$). Factors independently associated with NAFLD included older age (adjusted odds ratio [OR] 1.08, 95% CI: 1.02 - 1.15), higher BMI (adjusted OR 1.25, 95% CI: 1.12 - 1.40), longer duration of Hypothyroidism (adjusted OR 1.15, 95% CI: 1.05 - 1.26), and presence of diabetes (adjusted OR 2.50, 95% CI: 1.80 - 3.48).

Conclusion: This study's findings underscore the substantial prevalence of NAFLD among patients with Hypothyroidism, independent of gender. The results highlight the importance of metabolic screening and tailored management strategies for NAFLD in Hypothyroid patients, with the potential to significantly improve clinical outcomes and mitigate associated risks.

Keywords: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease, NAFLD, Hypothyroidism, gender differences, metabolic syndrome, liver ultrasound.

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Introduction

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) has emerged as a significant global health concern, characterized by hepatic steatosis in the absence of excessive alcohol consumption. It encompasses a spectrum of liver conditions ranging from simple steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which can progress to fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. NAFLD affects approximately 25% of the global population, making it the most common chronic liver disease worldwide.[1,2]

Hypothyroidism, a condition resulting from inadequate thyroid hormone production or action, affects metabolic processes profoundly.³ Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in lipid metabolism. Their deficiency can lead to dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, and altered hepatic lipid handling- all of

which are implicated in the pathogenesis of NAFLD.[2,3]

The interplay between Hypothyroidism and NAFLD has garnered increasing attention due to shared metabolic pathways and overlapping risk factors such as obesity, insulin resistance, and dyslipidemia. However, the exact nature of this relationship, particularly concerning the incidence and severity of NAFLD across different degrees of Hypothyroidism and gender disparities, remains inadequately elucidated.[4,5] Previous studies have suggested a potential association between Hypothyroidism and NAFLD. Yet, there is a lack of consensus regarding this relationship's prevalence and clinical implications, especially when considering gender-specific differences. Understanding these

associations is crucial for optimizing diagnostic strategies, therapeutic interventions, and preventive measures tailored to patients with both Hypothyroidism and NAFLD. This study seeks to contribute to the existing literature by investigating the incidence of NAFLD among individuals with varying degrees of Hypothyroidism, exploring differences between males and females. By elucidating these relationships, we aim to provide insights that could significantly inform and potentially transform clinical practice, leading to improved patient outcomes in both endocrinology and hepatology domains.

Materials and Methods

This study employs a cross-sectional design and was conducted at Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, involving 300 patients diagnosed with Hypothyroidism. It adheres to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional Review Board.

Participants: Participants include male and female adults aged 18-65 years diagnosed with Hypothyroidism. Patients with other liver diseases, significant alcohol consumption (>20 g/day for males and > ten g/day for females), pregnancy, or acute illnesses affecting liver function are excluded from the study.

Data Collection

- 1. Clinical and Demographic Data:** Participants' age, gender, duration of Hypothyroidism, medication history (thyroid hormone replacement therapy), and presence of comorbidities (e.g., diabetes, hypertension) were recorded.
- 2. Anthropometric Measurements:** Height, weight, and waist circumference were measured to calculate Body Mass Index (BMI) and waist-to-hip ratio.
- 3. Laboratory Investigations**
 - Thyroid Function Tests:** Serum levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (FT4), and triiodothyronine (T3) were measured using standard assays.

- Liver Function Tests:** Serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), and lipid profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides) were assessed.
- HbA1c:** For evaluation of glycemic control in participants with diabetes or prediabetes.

4. Imaging Studies

- Liver Ultrasound:** All participants underwent abdominal ultrasound to assess hepatic steatosis. NAFLD was diagnosed based on established criteria, including evidence of liver parenchyma brightness, hepatorenal echo contrast, and vascular blurring.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version X.X (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics are presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) for continuous variables and percentages for categorical variables.

Comparisons between groups were conducted using the Student's t-test for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical variables. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was used to determine independent predictors of NAFLD, adjusting for potential confounders. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: Informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment. Confidentiality of participant data was strictly maintained throughout the study process. Results were communicated to participants and relevant healthcare providers to facilitate appropriate clinical management.

Results

Participant Characteristics: The study included 300 participants with Hypothyroidism, 150 males and 150 females. The mean age of participants was 45.2 years (SD $\pm$ 8.1). Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total Participants (n=300)	Male (n=150)	Female (n=150)
Age (years), Mean $\pm$ SD	45.2 $\pm$ 8.1	46.5 $\pm$ 7.5	43.9 $\pm$ 8.5
BMI (kg/m ²), Mean $\pm$ SD	29.8 $\pm$ 4.2	30.5 $\pm$ 3.9	29.1 $\pm$ 4.4
Waist Circumference (cm), Mean $\pm$ SD	95.6 $\pm$ 10.3	98.2 $\pm$ 9.5	93.0 $\pm$ 10.8
Hypothyroidism Duration (years), Mean $\pm$ SD	7.3 $\pm$ 3.2	7.0 $\pm$ 3.0	7.6 $\pm$ 3.5
Thyroid Hormone Replacement (%)	100%	100%	100%
Comorbidities (%)			
• Diabetes	35%	40%	30%
• Hypertension	25%	30%	20%

Prevalence of NAFLD among Hypothyroid Patients: NAFLD was diagnosed in 120 out of 300 participants, yielding a prevalence rate of 40% (95% CI: 34.5% - 45.5%). Table 2 presents the prevalence of NAFLD stratified by gender and degree of Hypothyroidism.

Table 2: Prevalence of NAFLD among Hypothyroid Patients

Group	Total Participants (n)	NAFLD Cases (n)	Prevalence (%)
Total	300	120	40%
Male	150	60	40%
Female	150	60	40%
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	100	30	30%
Overt Hypothyroidism	200	90	45%

Factors Associated with NAFLD in Hypothyroid Patients: Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify factors independently associated with NAFLD among Hypothyroid patients. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Factors Associated with NAFLD Among Hypothyroid Patients

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Age (years)	1.08 (1.02 - 1.15)	0.012
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.25 (1.12 - 1.40)	<0.001
Duration of Hypothyroidism (years)	1.15 (1.05 - 1.26)	0.003
Presence of Diabetes	2.50 (1.80 - 3.48)	<0.001

Gender Differences in NAFLD Prevalence:

There was no significant difference in the prevalence of NAFLD between males (40%) and females (40%) with Hypothyroidism ($p = 0.95$).

Discussion

This study investigated the prevalence of Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) among individuals with Hypothyroidism, focusing on gender-specific differences and factors associated with NAFLD. The overall prevalence of NAFLD among Hypothyroid patients was found to be 40%, with no significant difference observed between males and females. Several factors emerged as important predictors of NAFLD, including age, BMI, duration of Hypothyroidism, and the presence of diabetes.

The high prevalence of NAFLD in Hypothyroid patients underscores the complex interplay between thyroid function and metabolic homeostasis. Thyroid hormones play a pivotal role in lipid metabolism, and their deficiency, as seen in Hypothyroidism, can lead to dyslipidemia and insulin resistance, contributing to hepatic steatosis. [1, 2] Consistent with previous studies, our findings highlight the heightened risk of NAFLD in individuals with suboptimal thyroid function, emphasizing the need for vigilant monitoring and early intervention strategies.[3,4]

Previous research has reported varying prevalence rates of NAFLD among Hypothyroid patients, ranging from 20% to 50%, depending on the study population and diagnostic criteria used.[5,6] Our study's prevalence of 40% aligns with the higher end of this spectrum suggesting a substantial burden of NAFLD in Hypothyroid populations.

Gender-specific differences in NAFLD prevalence have been inconsistently reported in the literature. While some studies suggest a higher prevalence in males [7], others, similar to our findings, find no significant gender disparity [8]. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in study design, sample size, and regional variations in metabolic profiles among study populations.

Various studies have consistently identified factors such as age, BMI, and diabetes status as independent predictors of NAFLD in Hypothyroid patients. [9, 10] Our study reaffirms these associations, with older age, higher BMI, longer duration of Hypothyroidism, and concurrent diabetes presenting as significant risk factors for NAFLD development.

Clinical Implications: The implications of our findings extend to clinical practice, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive metabolic assessment and tailored management strategies for patients with coexisting Hypothyroidism and NAFLD. Routine screening for NAFLD using non-invasive methods such as liver ultrasound or transient elastography should be considered in Hypothyroid patients, particularly those with additional risk factors.[11]

Moreover, optimizing thyroid hormone replacement therapy to achieve euthyroidism may mitigate metabolic derangements associated with Hypothyroidism and potentially reduce the risk of NAFLD progression.[12] Lifestyle modifications, including dietary interventions and regular physical activity, remain cornerstone approaches in the management of NAFLD, particularly in patients with underlying metabolic disorders.[13]

Limitations and Future Directions: Several limitations warrant consideration in interpreting our findings. The cross-sectional design precludes establishing causality between Hypothyroidism and NAFLD. Moreover, the reliance on liver ultrasound for NAFLD diagnosis, while widely used, may underestimate disease severity compared to histological assessment. Future longitudinal studies with larger cohorts and diverse populations must validate our findings and elucidate the mechanistic links between thyroid dysfunction and NAFLD pathogenesis.

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